

MARKETING GOALS AND THE QUALITY SYSTEM IN THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

Economics

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Eshija Shehabi

Faculty of Economics. University "Fadil Sulejmani", Tetova. North Macedonia.

Abstract

Industry is an economic activity that takes place from the raw material to the final production. An industry is a group of related enterprises based on their primary business activities. In modern economies, there are dozens of industry classifications, which are usually grouped into larger categories called sectors. A group of companies with their sectors collaborate to produce a final product. Individual businesses or companies are usually classified in an industry based on their largest sources of revenue. The goals of individual or grouped companies are achieved only with a common marketing mission and with a genuine quality system.

Introduction

Always the main goal of an industry is the interest (profit) that the manager has planned for the realization of his management. The goals of the industry define the tasks of the manager. Achieving the goal of the industry will contribute to its achievement of the set mission. The objectives of the mission are to develop it. They are the basis of strategies, plans, priorities, resource distribution and the starting point of any management action (Shuklev, 2013, p. 127).

To manage the goals of the industry means to manage the tasks of the enterprise at all processes and at all levels. For the objectivity of the tools, the industry has assigned tasks to all processes and levels. Their determination to create opportunities and clarify goals (profit, increase sales, increase market share, risk diversification, etc.) at every level in industry, management connects the management objectives of a particular system (Ristevska-Jovanovska, 2012, p.23). The goals of industry are what industry strives to achieve and what it wants to measure, its activity in the context of the mission (Durankiev, 2010, p. 58). Marketing is a very important element of strategic contracts: the basic needs of consumers, the development of narrow goals and priorities in introduction, employees' perceptions of quality and performance, helping employees to collaborate (to connect system and price and support quality management).

The mission of the industry (what it has decided as a goal since its inception) may in some cases be unclear, or need modification due to environmental conditions that may be unattainable (Ristevska-Jovanovska, 2012, p. 23). The mission consists of five basic elements:

- a) Industry development level
- b) Personal parameters and goals of the owners and management of the industry
- c) Environmental conditions
- d) The amount of available funds, and
- e) The specific state of the industry to achieve long-term goals.

Marketing Mission

The industry mission reflects the intention or reason for the industry's decline. A well-defined mission establishes the main goal for an industry to be different from other similar industries, defining the scope of general activities in relation to the products that will be offered and served in the markets (Shuklev, 2013, p.127).

Goal setting and industry objectivity means that decision-making should create opportunities to define goals (profit, increase sales, increase market share, risk diversification, etc.). At each level of industry management, all of these are connected in a specific system - management goals (Ristevska-Jovanovska, 2012, p.23). The goals of industry is often an important starting point for effective management (Figure 3.5-1). Achieving industry will help achieve the mission. Objectives in terms of: strategies, plans, priorities, resource distribution are the starting point of any management action (Shuklev, 2013, p. 127).

Quality is one of the main goals of any business. In product development, you first need to choose the level of quality that will hold the position of the selected product in the market. Here, product quality indicates the ability of the requested product to respond to its functions. It includes a full product sustainability, relevance, accuracy, ease of treatment, and other valuable attributes. While some of these attributes can be measured objectively, from a marketing point of view, quality should be measured in terms of consumer perception capability. The industry chooses a level of quality that agrees with the requirements of the selected market and the level of quality of competing products (Ristevska-Jovanovska, 2012, p.117).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a marketing strategy based on customer behavior

Customer style
Experience

Source: Durankiev B., 2010, "Marketing" Sofia, UNSS, p. 100

The goals of the quality system give importance to the industry because they are based on achieving the goals set in the quality policy. These levels of quality include all levels of sales, production, design, storage, etc. It is important for industry to apply the above levels in order for all its objectives to be in line with quality policy. Implementing all the rules set out in the quality policy gives priority to achieving quality goals and contributes to the development of a quality management system. Also, all these quality goals that are included in the quality policy should be treated with more attention by the CEO, because the purpose of the industry and their achievement depends on what the director decides.

Marketing Purposes and Quality Systems in Production

In the theory and practice of the range of marketing lists, the characteristics of the products make their value of use. In this regard, there are several differences in the understanding of some signs, etc. However, apart from the price, which is very important, the other differences are (Gramatikov, 2004, p.51):

- Product design
- Product quality
- Product functionality
- Product brand
- Product packaging (packaging)
- servicing products, etc.

Figure 2. Basic marketing system

Source: Ristevska-Jovanovska S. and Jakovski B. 2003, “Strategic Marketing”, Skopje, Faculty of Economics, p.7.

In this sense, marketing is based on some basic concepts (Ristevska-Jovanovska and Jakovski 2003, p.5):

1. The concept of needs, desires and demand, which considers human needs and desires as the starting point of marketing;
2. The concept of needs, which can be offered to satisfy the needs or desires through certain products, regardless of whether the product appears in physical form or as a service;
3. The concept of satisfied value indicates the degree of fulfillment of the need;
4. The concept of exchanges and transactions that are realized between two or more market participants;
5. The concept of markets puts customers in a potential focus, where society, through the exchange of products and values, meets the needs of the participants.

In addition, the industry has a choice of alternative strategies to an increasing number of product types that are classified in different ways and by different criteria. Onfor example, strategies can be classified as stated below (Ristevska-Jovanovska S. and Jakovski B. 2003, "Strategic Marketing", Skopje, Faculty of Economics, pp. 14-15):

- Strategies in industry
- Sector-level strategies
- Strategies at the level of business functions
- Strategies that are in range
- Strategies in a broader sense
- Strategies in a narrower sense

According to the function:

- Marketing strategies
- Financial strategies
- Development strategies and requirements
- Staff strategies
- Profit strategies, etc.
- Personal strategies
- Strategies for managers' values

- Motivation
- Methods for environmental analysis
- Methods of self-employment
- Technical communication with people
- Meeting basic needs
- Strategies depending on the level of realization
- Intended strategies
- Strategies of realization
- Thoughtful strategies
- Unrealized strategies
- Unexpected strategies

The formation of marketing strategies are influenced by many factors (Figure 3.6-3) and above all are the factors that affect the functioning of the environment of the industry, then the organizational state of the industry, the life cycle of the market, products and more. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Factors influencing the marketing strategy

Source: Ristevska-Jovanovska S. and Jakovski B. 2003, “Strategic Marketing”, Skopje, Faculty of Economics, p.14.

The choice of strategies is closely related to product design (Figure 4). The way the product will be designed will also depend on the chosen marketing strategy and other industry strategies, because product design comes as a result of selected strategies.

Figure 4. Alternative product and service strategies

Products / Markets	Existing products	Improvement in existing products	New products with market technologies		New products with unrelated technology
			Manipulation with the range	Increase product diversity	
Existing markets	(1) Market penetration strategies	(2) Reform strategies	(3) Replacement strategies	(4) Product Line Expansion Strategies	(5) Horizontal diversification strategies
New markets	(6) Market development strategies	(7) Market Expansion Strategies	(8) Market segmentation strategies-differentiation strategies	(9) Strategies of Concentric Diversification	(10) Strategies of conglomerate diversification
Resources and distributions	(11) forward and / or backward integration strategies				

Source: Ristevska-Jovanovska S. and Jakovski B. 2003, “Strategic Marketing”, Skopje, Faculty of Economics, p.15.

The industry can choose to design or design their own products, or just develop existing products, planning everything to be included in the process, ie to consider the technical possibilities available to them to achieve that design. The industry designs new products or develops its products depending on its customers.

Conclusion

It has been proven that small and medium-sized businesses need to implement quality standards; industry needs to support existing quality standards and improve them.

In every industry there are their standards for their products / services, they implement and update the international standards to prove their own capabilities and for marketing purposes.

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